

DISCRETE MODELING OF ARBITRARY MATRIX CRACKING AND DELAMINATIONS IN LAMINATED COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

Matrix cracking and delamination initiation, propagation, and interaction prediction in laminated composites without any prior knowledge and/or meshing of matrix cracking surfaces was accomplished by combining stress and fracture mechanics-based constitutive modeling within a mesh-independent crack-modeling framework. Tensile loading of a quasi-isotropic laminate was performed and shown to capture the correct delamination sequence, evolving from randomly generated matrix cracks, as well as the failure load values.

Keywords: Composite, laminate, delamination, cracking, deformation

INTRODUCTION

Prediction of matrix cracking and delamination and their interaction represents the foundation of the analysis framework required for efficient and reliable utilization of laminated composites in contemporary environments. Significant progress has been achieved to date in developing numerical approaches and underlying constitutive models for initiation and propagation of specific damage modes and delaminations in particular. Since delamination surfaces coincide with morphological features such as ply interfaces they can be represented by the opening of doubled nodes using existing finite element tools.

Other damage modes, such as matrix cracking, do not allow straightforward general treatment within the framework of traditional finite element tools. Indeed, creation of a finite element mesh which accommodates the boundaries and features, e.g. holes, for a composite laminate and cracks with different orientation in different plies is a formidable challenge. At the same time recent work [1], where a limited amount of initially predefined matrix cracks and inter-ply delaminations were modeled in quasi-isotropic laminates, shows the critical importance of such analysis.

The usefulness of mesh-independent crack (MIC) modeling methods in composite failure analysis has been recognized for quite some time [2-3]. Over the last decade much research was devoted to this topic following the pioneering work of Moes, et al. [4] in which the concept of x-FEM was proposed. Although most of

the research was devoted to arbitrary crack propagation in isotropic materials, recent application to composite materials includes delamination modeling and textile composite architecture representation [5]. A recent publication [6] provides a review of contemporary development of the field as well as novel applications of x-FEM to interfacial cracking analysis in two- and three-dimensional settings. It is conceptually straightforward to model matrix cracking by using x-FEM in a given ply with arbitrary orientation; however, it is more difficult to model matrix cracks crossing over each other in adjacent plies and the delaminations that these cracks may induce. Within the traditional x-FEM approach, this issue could be addressed by developing a special enrichment for multiple crack situations or connecting two enriched/cracked elements. Such connection is rather transparent in the framework of the Hansbo and Hansbo [7] formulation where the displacement discontinuity inside the element is projected into the (phantom) nodes by continuation of the partitioned shape functions. In this case an update of the interface properties in the vicinity of the cracked elements would be required to account for the change of the surface area associated with the node due to its shape function representing only a portion of the element, which would in principle not represent a major difficulty. Recently such capability was demonstrated in the quasi-two-dimensional formulation [8].

The purpose of the present manuscript is to propose a numerical approach capable of modeling the origination and evolution of complex matrix cracking and delamination networks in laminated composites without any prior knowledge or assumptions regarding the locations of damage origination. A MIC modeling method proposed by Iarve [9], which represents a regularized x-FEM approach, is extended to achieve this objective in a fully three-dimensional formulation, which has not been demonstrated to date. In a regularized formulation, the step function describing the crack surface is replaced by a continuous function and consequently allows one to maintain a Gauss integration schema for element stiffness matrix computation without regard to cracking orientation. In this case the connection between the two cracked surfaces can be established either by nodal spring connection or through shape function integrals, as is the route chosen below.

MESH INDEPENDENT CRACK MODELING

Regularized Displacement Approximation Enrichment

The main elements of the regularized MIC modeling are discussed below. The MIC surface Γ_α is described by means of the signed distance function defined as:

$$f_\alpha(\mathbf{x}) = \text{sign}(\mathbf{n}(\bar{\mathbf{x}})(\mathbf{x} - \bar{\mathbf{x}})) \min_{\bar{\mathbf{x}} \in \Gamma_\alpha} \|\mathbf{x} - \bar{\mathbf{x}}\| \quad (1)$$

The traditional x-FEM strong discontinuity formulation is based on the element enrichment with displacement modes discontinuous over the crack surface by introducing shape functions multiplied by $H(f_a(\mathbf{x}))$, where $H(x)$ is the Heaviside step

function. Consider a partition of unity set of continuous basis displacement approximation functions $X_i(\mathbf{x})$ on the domain of interest V .

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i \in \Omega} X_i(\mathbf{x}) \mathbf{u}_i, \quad (2)$$

In the regularized formulation [9] the Heaviside step function is replaced with a continuous function $\tilde{H}(\mathbf{x})$

$$\tilde{H}(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i \in \Omega} X_i(\mathbf{x}) h_i$$

where $X_i(\mathbf{x})$ are the same shape functions as in Eqn. (2). The coefficients h_i are calculated as follows

$$\square_i = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \frac{\int_V f_\alpha(\mathbf{x}) X_i(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x}}{\int_V |f_\alpha(\mathbf{x})| X_i(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x}} \right) \quad (3)$$

This definition involves only continuous functions and can be calculated by using standard Gauss quadratures. Clearly the only coefficients h_i , which are not equal to 0 or 1 are those whose shape functions are divided by the crack surface. Let us denote the set of all index values in Eqn. (3) for which h_i is not equal to 0 or 1 by Ω_α . Then the enriched approximation [9] for the domain V and arbitrary crack is defined in the following form

$$\mathbf{u} = \tilde{H} \mathbf{u}^{(1)} + (1 - \tilde{H}) \mathbf{u}^{(2)} + \mathbf{u}^{(3)}, \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{u}^{(1)} = \sum_{i \in \Omega_\alpha} X_i \mathbf{U}_i^{(1)}, \quad \mathbf{u}^{(2)} = \sum_{i \in \Omega_\alpha} X_i \mathbf{U}_i^{(2)}, \quad (5)$$

and

$$\mathbf{u}^{(3)} = \sum_{i \in \Omega / \Omega_\alpha} X_i \mathbf{U}_i^{(3)} \quad (6)$$

We have also omitted the spatial argument for conciseness. The displacement approximation given in Eqn. (4) contains the enrichment in the crack region via displacement fields $\mathbf{u}^{(1)}$ and $\mathbf{u}^{(2)}$ as well as the unchanged shape functions away from the crack $\mathbf{u}^{(3)}$. Expressions (4)-(6) define the enriched displacement approximation by essentially replacing each original shape function X_i , $i \in \Omega_a$ with two shape functions, $\tilde{H} X_i$ and $(1 - \tilde{H}) X_i$. This approximation was applied in [9] in conjunction with a higher order C^0 displacement approximation (p-elements) as well as B-spline approximation of displacements, where the coefficients \mathbf{U}_i do not correspond to nodal displacements. The convenience of such representation of the enrichment lies in the simplicity of bookkeeping the connectivity, where the two copies of the shape function do not interact and are connected with only \tilde{H} or $(1 - \tilde{H})$ multiple copies of the other enriched shape function if their supports overlap.

In the case of the original strong discontinuity x-FEM framework, when $\tilde{H}(\mathbf{x})=H(f_a(\mathbf{x}))$, one arrives at well-known formulations [7], where the notion of duplicating a shape function partitioned across the crack surface is equivalent to introducing duplicate nodes, since a one-to-one correspondence of shape functions and nodes is present. The strain energy increment in the volume, V , with displacement approximation given in Eqn. (4) is written as

$$\begin{aligned} \delta W = \int_V \left\{ \tilde{H}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{(1)} - \mathbf{e})^T \mathbf{C} \delta(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{(1)} - \mathbf{e}) + (1 - \tilde{H})(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{(2)} - \mathbf{e})^T \mathbf{C} \delta(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{(2)} - \mathbf{e}) + \right. \\ \left. + (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{(3)} - \mathbf{e})^T \mathbf{C} \delta(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{(3)} - \mathbf{e}) \right. \\ \left. + \tilde{H}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{(1)} - \mathbf{e})^T \mathbf{C} \delta(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{(3)} - \mathbf{e}) + (1 - \tilde{H})(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{(2)} - \mathbf{e})^T \mathbf{C} \delta(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{(3)} - \mathbf{e}) \right. \\ \left. + \tilde{H}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{(3)} - \mathbf{e})^T \mathbf{C} \delta(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{(1)} - \mathbf{e}) + (1 - \tilde{H})(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{(3)} - \mathbf{e})^T \mathbf{C} \delta(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{(2)} - \mathbf{e}) \right\} dV \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where \mathbf{C} is the elastic orthotropic stiffness tensor, and \mathbf{e} is the nonmechanical strain tensor, so that

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - \mathbf{e}) \quad (8)$$

The nonmechanical strain is required to account for the residual stress state arising in composite laminates due to the curing process and is $\mathbf{e}=(T-T_0)\boldsymbol{\alpha}$. Therefore, $T-T_0$ is the difference between the cure and room temperature, and $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ is the tensor of thermal expansion coefficients. The constitutive relationship (7) is written for each ply, and the stiffness tensor and thermal expansion strain tensor are both obtained from the unidirectional ply properties by using appropriate tensor rotation rules depending upon the fiber orientation in that ply.

The increment of work of the external traction \mathbf{T} applied at the portion S_T of the boundary ∂V is expressed as

$$\delta A = \int_{S_T} \mathbf{T} \delta \mathbf{u} dS, \quad (9)$$

DELAMINATION AND MIC PROPAGATION

Decohesive formulation

The mode-sensitive decohesive constitutive proposed in Ref. [10] is applied in the present paper. The increment of energy dissipated over an interface S_n between the n and $n+1^{\text{st}}$ plies when the displacement gap increases by $\delta(\Delta \mathbf{u})$ is

$$\delta K_n = \iint_{S_n} \mathbf{P} \cdot \delta(\Delta \mathbf{u}) ds \quad (10)$$

where the decohesive force \mathbf{P} is a function of the displacement gap $\Delta \mathbf{u}=\mathbf{u}_1-\mathbf{u}_2$, and \mathbf{u}_1 , \mathbf{u}_2 are vectors of displacement on the surface S_n in the n^{th} and $n+1^{\text{st}}$ plies,

respectively. Vector \mathbf{P} is dependent on the mode mixity coefficient $B = 1 - \frac{(|\Delta u_n| + \Delta u_n)^2}{4(\Delta u)^2}$ and $\Delta u = |\Delta \mathbf{u}|$, $\Delta u_n = (\Delta \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n})$, where \mathbf{n} is outward normal vector to the surface with displacement vector \mathbf{u}_2 . The following material parameters define the magnitude of \mathbf{P} : tensile and shear strength Y, S ; critical values of energy release rate (ERR) for Mode I and II delamination and $\eta=2.25$, which is obtained from one mixed-mode delamination test.

MIC propagation

In the regularized formulation, the crack propagation is governed by the constitutive properties in the gradient zone [11], in which $|\nabla \tilde{H}| = \sqrt{\nabla \tilde{H} \cdot \nabla \tilde{H}} > 0$. In Ref. [11] this zone is treated as a transition region with constitutive properties derived from that of the bulk properties; we, however, insert the decohesive constitutive relationship of interface fracture directly. The increment of the energy dissipated at a given point as a function of the displacement gap increment is given by Eqn. (9), thus the total increment of the dissipated energy for a crack with surface Γ_α can be expressed as a surface integral over the crack area in a way identical to (10). To evaluate the incremental energy dissipated for the MIC, we express the surface integral in Eqn. (10) as a volume integral by using the Dirack's delta function of signed distance function $\delta_D(f_\alpha)$

$$\delta M = \int_V \delta_D(f_\alpha) \mathbf{P} \delta(\Delta \mathbf{u}) dV$$

We replaced δK with δM to differentiate between delaminations and intra-ply MICs. In the case of the regularized MIC formulation, the function $\delta_D(f_\alpha)$ is replaced by $|\nabla \tilde{H}|$ and the energy dissipation becomes

$$\delta M = \int_V |\nabla \tilde{H}| \mathbf{P} \delta(\Delta \mathbf{u}) dV \quad (11)$$

In the case of the MIC, the displacement gap is calculated as a difference between the displacement fields $\mathbf{u}^{(1)}$ and $\mathbf{u}^{(2)}$ in the enriched approximation (4), and the normal vector to the MIC "surface" is $\mathbf{n} = \nabla f_\alpha$. The mode mixity parameter is then computed in a way identical to the case of surface delamination, as mentioned above.

COMBINED MODELING OF INTER-PLY DELAMINATION AND INTRA-PLY CRACKING.

Equations (7), (9) and (11) describe the deformation and fracture of a given orthotropic ply. We have not used additional indexes to designate all of these parameters to a specific ply $n=1, \dots, N$. For further discussion, however, we introduce such an index and write down the global energy balance equation as

$$\sum_{n=1}^N (\delta W_n + \delta M_n - \delta A_n) + \sum_{n=1}^{N-1} \delta K_n = 0, \quad (12)$$

where the interface delaminations are accounted for by Eqn. (10). In the case when MICs are present in the adjacent plies, the displacements \mathbf{u}_1 and \mathbf{u}_2 are enriched according to Eqns. (5) and (6). When regularized enrichment is used, the integration of all shape functions is conducted on the original Gauss points, and thereby is straightforward for arbitrary enrichment of displacements in the adjacent plies. Two sparse matrices \mathbf{F}_n^1 and \mathbf{F}_n^2 are formed at the interface between plies n and $n+1$. For each integration point (always common for plies n and $n+1$) on the interface (row index), these matrices contain the values of all non-zero shape functions in this point (column index) for the ply $n+1$ (displacement \mathbf{u}_1) and ply n (displacement \mathbf{u}_2), respectively. These matrices have large dimensions but are very sparse. The contribution of variation of the delamination terms in Eqn. (12) to the global stiffness matrix can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{K} = \sum_{n=1}^{N-1} (\mathbf{F}_n^1 - \mathbf{F}_n^2)^T \mathbf{D} (\mathbf{F}_n^1 - \mathbf{F}_n^2) \quad (13)$$

The weight matrix \mathbf{D} is a diagonal matrix containing the Gauss weights and Jacobian at the given integration point multiplied by the cohesive stiffness. Note that the matrices \mathbf{F}_n can also be used to compute the displacement gap $\Delta \mathbf{u}$ in each integration point by simple multiplication $(\mathbf{F}_n^1 - \mathbf{F}_n^2) \mathbf{U}$ after the solution vector $\mathbf{U} = (\mathbf{U}^{(1)}, \dots, \mathbf{U}^{(2)}, \dots, \mathbf{U}^{(3)}, \dots)$. By knowing the displacement gap one can update the coefficient of decohesive stiffness in each integration point.

The opening of the MICs in individual plies, Eqn. (12), is handled in a way similar to the opening of delaminations, Eqn. (13). For opening of the MICs, the matrices of shape function values in integration points are formed so that $\mathbf{F}_n^{(1)}$ and $\mathbf{F}_n^{(2)}$ contain the functions corresponding to enrichments $\mathbf{u}^{(1)}$ and $\mathbf{u}^{(2)}$, respectively, and the components of the weight matrix, which we denote $\tilde{\mathbf{D}}$ to distinguish from the delamination case \mathbf{D} , are the products of Gauss weight, Jacobean, $|\nabla \tilde{H}|$ and the decohesive stiffness in the given integration point. Thus the contribution of variation of the MIC opening energy in all plies to the total stiffness matrix can be written as

$$\mathbf{M} = \sum_{n=1}^N (\mathbf{F}_n^{(1)} - \mathbf{F}_n^{(2)})^T \tilde{\mathbf{D}} (\mathbf{F}_n^{(1)} - \mathbf{F}_n^{(2)}) \quad (14)$$

The variation of strain energy terms W_n leads to a standard stiffness matrix component expression, where the stiffness matrix in each integration point is multiplied by \tilde{H} or by $(1 - \tilde{H})$, or is unmodified. Denoting the contribution of variation of the strain energy terms, Eqn. (11), to the total stiffness matrix as \mathbf{W} , one can write

$$(\mathbf{W}+\mathbf{M}+\mathbf{K})\mathbf{U}=\lambda\mathbf{Q}_0+\mathbf{N}, \quad (15)$$

where $\lambda\mathbf{Q}_0$ is the parametric external load vector and \mathbf{N} reflects the nonmechanical strain contributions. The system of equations (15) contains highly nonlinear components \mathbf{M} and \mathbf{K} and is solved by using the Newton-Raphson method for defined load increments $\Delta\lambda$.

MULTIPLE PARALLEL MIC MODELING AND ORIGINATION

In the present study our goal is to model networks of parallel matrix cracks in a composite laminate as described above. A ply containing $s=1, \dots, S$ cracks parallel to the direction of fiber defined by angle θ is considered. Denote by f_s the signed distance function, Eqn. (1) of the individual crack, which is fully defined by coordinates of its origin \mathbf{x}_s and orientation θ . The function ϕ is used to define the set Ω_α of enriched shape functions in Eqn. (3) instead of f_α

$$\phi = \prod_{s=1}^S f_s. \quad (16)$$

Function ϕ maintains some key features of the signed distance function for each of the s cracks in the ply under consideration. This function changes sign over the faces of each crack, and its gradient $\nabla\phi$ is perpendicular to the surface of each crack. As follows from Eqns. (3), the enrichment is triggered by the change of sign of f_α rather than by its value, and thus replacing it with Eqn. (16) extends the previous discussion to multiple parallel MICs in each ply. Initially no MICs are assumed and only thermal loading is applied at $\lambda=0$. The loading parameter is then incremented by $\Delta\lambda$. In the beginning of each load step the LaRC03 failure criterion [12] is checked at each integration point. If it is exceeded a MIC is inserted and ϕ recalculated by using Eqn. (16). All matrices in Eqn. (13) as well as vectors \mathbf{Q}_0 and \mathbf{N} are reformed with the new ϕ . Then the Newton-Raphson iterations are started with only matrices \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{M} updated at each step. We chose in our implementation to update the MIC opening matrix \mathbf{M} outside the strain energy matrix calculation to increase the calculation efficiency. Note that in the FE formulation, it is usually calculated at the element level simultaneously with the strain energy portion of the stiffness matrix.

TENSILE LOADING OF A QUASI-ISOTROPIC LAMINATE

Detailed investigation of the delamination mechanisms in quasi-isotropic laminates has been recently accomplished in [1]. Experimentation as well as high fidelity finite element (FE) analysis was performed on IM7/8552 specimens stacking sequence $[45_m/90_m/-45_m/0_m]_s$ for $m=1, \dots, 8$. This laminate exhibits a complex delamination failure mode initiating at the outer 45/90 interface and stepping to the inside surfaces via matrix cracks in the 90 and -45 plies. The

authors identified a relatively simple matrix cracking pattern that was incorporated in a finite element model that allowed predicting the load drop caused by the delamination. This matrix cracking pattern is shown in Figure 1, and consists of one matrix crack in each ply. This pattern was modeled by a 3-D FEA model, where all three cracks were meshed beforehand and considered open from the beginning. The delamination between each ply was modeled.

Figure 1. A 3-crack model capable of predicting the delamination load and sequence of the $[45_4/90_4/-45_4/0_4]_s$ IM7/8552 laminate

The methodology presented above was applied to perform the fracture analysis of this laminate without any predefined matrix cracks or delaminations. Although the problem under consideration, namely fracture analysis of a quasi-isotropic laminate, appears to be a relatively simple case with respect to other practically important configurations, it requires introduction of random variation of material parameters to accomplish the simulation. Indeed, the stress fields predicted under tensile loading conditions are highly uniform in the axial direction except in the edge region. The stress relaxation, which occurs in the vicinity of a matrix crack inside a ply, and stress concentration in the surrounding plies have a very local nature, and the cracking pattern is affected by computer number roundup pattern. A field of Weibull distributed, volume-weighted strength fields [13] were introduced in each ply with the Weibull shape parameter of $\alpha=12$ (coefficient of variation~8%), according to [14]. The typical load deflection curve obtained for one of the realizations of the stochastic strength field is shown by the solid green line in Figure 2. The vertical dashes along the loading curve designate the loads at which the cracks are inserted in the 90-degree ply (dark or blue lines), the 45-degree ply (lighter or red lines) and the -45-degree ply (light or green lines). In the simulation the number of cracks inserted in each ply was limited to 15. The analysis methodology correctly predicted both the sequence of the delamination, the failure loads and the multistep load drop behavior before the final failure that was experimentally recorded in [1]. The load carried after the delamination process is that by the 0 plies until fiber failure. The result of the simulation based on the 3 predefined crack model, similar to one in [1], is also shown in Figure 2 by the dotted blue line. In this case the load drop is sudden, and no softening behavior is observed due to subcritical damage accumulation. Note that the failure load is very close to that predicted by the stochastic simulation of crack initiation and experimental value of 541 MPa, Ref. [1]. Figure 3 displays the z-direction displacement map for three simulation load steps. The first two show accumulation of the

Figure 2. Stress displacement tensile loading curve of the quasi-isotropic laminate illustrating random crack insertion load values.

45 cracks in the top ply. The third displacement shown was obtained at the load step immediately preceding the complete delamination and displays a pattern very similar to the delamination sequence previously observed in the 3- crack delamination model. Initially the delaminations also occur at the 45/90 interface, however at multiple locations at the ends of 45 cracks, and cause initial load drop, which was not present in the 3 crack model. Then the delamination step-down occurs in one of the crack locations through 90 and -45 cracks and leads to a delamination at the -45/0 interface, followed by and final load drop.

Figure 3. Vertical (z-direction) displacement map at the different load steps.

CONCLUSIONS

A fully three-dimensional methodology for modeling complex matrix cracking and delamination networks in laminated composites, based on regularized x-FEM formulation [9], is proposed. Detailed verification of the approach is not presented due to size limitation. An example of axial loading of quasi-isotropic laminate [1] is considered to demonstrate the methodology. Random distribution of the strength properties in each ply was applied and LaRC03 failure criterion used for automatic

crack generation at each load step of the nonlinear analysis. Good agreement with the experimental data was observed

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